

**Assessment of Emergency Victims' Satisfaction on Relief Services Provided by the State
Emergency Management Agency Kano State, Nigeria**

By

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Abstract

This study examines emergency victims' satisfaction on relief services provided by the State Emergency management agency Kano State, Nigeria. The objectives of the study were to determine the needs of emergency victims, the level of satisfaction on relief services provided to emergency victims and determine if there is significant relationship between the needs and satisfaction on relief services among emergency victims in Kano State. The study adopted a survey research design with population of 52,661 subjects comprising of 287 staff and 52,374 emergency victims who benefitted from the relief services provided by SEMA in Kano State. The sample of the study was 390 beneficiaries were selected and purposive sampling was employed in selecting 30 officials of KSEMA selected through the use of Snow bolling procedure. While two self-developed instruments were used in the collection of data namely Questionnaire and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) Guide, the validity of the instrument was ascertained by experts in the field of Measurement and evaluation, social work, and emergency management and reliability of the instruments was obtained using the split-half method in which the reliability coefficient level of 0.84 was obtained. Data was analyzed through the use of mean, frequency counts and percentage; while the data collected through the FGD were analysed by the use thematic analysis and the hypothesis was tested using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistics. The finding of the study revealed among others that there is significant relationship between needs and satisfaction on relief services among emergency victims in Kano State. The recommendations made by the study include Government and non-governmental organisations should mobilise other sources of external assistance/donations for supporting the provision of sufficient monetary donations that will facilitate occupational choices and career development among the emergency victims.

Keywords: Emergency victim, Emergency management, learned helplessness, Relief services, and Satisfaction

Introduction

Within the decade of 2010 to 2019, many victims of insurgencies from the North-East had migrated to Kano State in search of places to live and start a new beginning and the victims require relief services (Salkida, 2012, and IOM, 2016). Relief services are the immediate contemporary social work processes organized for the purpose of helping individuals and groups facing various social problems within the social system. Emergencies arise as a result of disasters, such as earthquake, volcano eruptions, storms, fire outbreaks, insurgencies, flood, drought, desertification and other forms of catastrophe requiring emergency responses, such as food items, home utensils, infrastructure, medication, counselling, clothes, etc. These forms of emergency responses are provided by responsible agencies effectively for the purpose of promoting the well-being of victims across societies.

Equally, the victims of Boko-Haram attacks in different places in Kano state in 19th January, 2013 resulted on many people were injured and need relief services. Consequently, the victims were found vulnerable with social, economic and psychological problems, such as crime, poverty, hunger, hopelessness, frustration, prostitution, unemployment, insecurity and many other social vices that can facilitate the abnormality of victims in Kano State which necessitates the assistance of KSEMA.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this study is based on the Learned Helplessness Theory developed by Seligman and Maier (1976). The theory posits that animals and people can learn that responding to situation controls rewards and punishment. They are all sensitive to the independence of responding and reinforcers and can learn that events are either uncontrollable or controllable. The theory stressed three main effects of uncontrollable trauma, which provide for learning in terms of response initiation, retardation of learning and emotional stress.

- i) Response initiation; that is the probability that the subject will initiate responses to escape is lowered because part of the incentive for making such responses is the expectation that they will bring relief;
- ii) Retardation of learning; that is learning that responding and shock are independent and make it more difficult to learn that responding does produce relief and
- iii) Emotional stress: that is learning that trauma is uncontrollable and may produce more stress than learning that it is controllable. (Seligman, 1967).

This means that people affected by emergencies can either make some responses or refrain from making ally, and thereby influence the events around them.

The theory is relevant to the study, as it highlights the situation of helplessness that emergency victims face. It also demonstrates the varying patterns of responses to helpless conditions, including the response in terms of relief support/services. These therefore create the need for interventional measures through active relief services provision, and which are expected to make them helpful and hopeful, as well as gain resettlement into their various social and economic lives and experience psychological stability.

Statement of the Problem

Contemporarily, relief services are various interventional programmes meant for the victims who were found vulnerable with social, economic and psychological problems, such as crime, poverty, hunger, hopelessness, frustration, prostitution, unemployment, insecurity and many other social vices that facilitates the abnormality of victims in our societies. Emergencies arise as a result of disasters, such as earthquake, volcano eruptions, storms, fire outbreaks, insurgencies, flood, drought, desertification and other forms of catastrophe requiring

emergency responses, such as food items, home utensils, infrastructure, medication, counselling, clothes, and many more. It was evident that the SEMA in Kano State was backed up by an enabling law of the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) Act No. 12 of 1999 and as amended by the Act No.50 of 1999 to act as a disaster management structure to formulate and implement policies that enhance the well-being of victims in such emergency situations. However, goods worth millions of Naira were provided to various categories of emergency victims. The aim was to enhance the quality of life and improve the well-being of the emergency victims in the State. It is in the light of the foregoing discourse that this paper intends to assess the emergency victims' satisfaction on relief services provided by the state emergency management agency Kano State, Nigeria.

Research Objectives

- The paper is guided by the following objectives:

- i. To determine the needs of victims of emergency who enjoy Relief Services provided by the State Emergency Management Agency Kano State, Nigeria -
- ii. To determine the level of satisfaction on relief services provided to emergency victims in Kano State, and
- iii. To determine if there is significant relationship between the needs and satisfaction on relief services among emergency victims in Kano State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in this study:

- i. What are the needs of victims of emergency who enjoy Relief Services provided by the State Emergency Management Agency Kano State, Nigeria?
- ii. What is the level of satisfaction on relief services provided to emergency victims in Kano State?

Research Hypothesis

The paper tested the following hypothesis:

- a. There is no significant relationship between the needs of emergency victims and satisfaction on the relief services provided by KSEMA.

Methodology

This study employed a survey research design and a population of 52,661 subjects comprising of 287 staff and 52,374 emergency victims respectively. A sample of 390 beneficiaries of relief services provided by KSEMA and 30 officials of the agency were selected by the use of snowballing and purposive sampling. Two self-developed instruments were used in the collection of data. These were a Questionnaire and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) Guide. A 4-point Likert Scale type Questionnaire named "Questionnaire for Emergency Victims of KSEMA" (QEVKSEMA) for the emergency victims was used and FGD was conducted for Officials of KSEMA who deliver the relief services. The validity of the instrument was ascertained by experts in measurement and evaluation, social work, and emergency management. And the reliability of the instruments was obtained using the split-half method in which the reliability coefficient level of 0.84 was obtained.

Data was analyzed through descriptive statistics in form of frequency (F) and percentage (%), mean (X) (High, Medium and Low to ascertain the level of satisfaction), and data generated from FGD was analysed through the use of thematic analysis. However, the decision rule for the acceptance of the statement on items of the questionnaire was guided by the used of cumulative-mean score at or above 2.50 in which a mean of 2.50 above is regarded as acceptance of the statement and a mean of below 2.50 is regarded as rejection of the statements. In addition, the hypothesis was tested by the use of Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistics.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the needs of emergency victims who enjoy Relief Services provided by the State Emergency Management Agency Kano State, Nigeria

Table 1. Needs of emergency victims

Immediate needs	SA		A		D		SD		\bar{X}	Decision
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
Security of life and property	188	54.2	81	23.3	36	10.4	42	12.1	3.1960	Accepted
Comfortable shelter	158	45.5	116	33.4	32	9.2	41	11.8	3.1268	Accepted
Essential food stuff	172	49.6	106	30.5	39	11.2	30	8.6	3.2104	Accepted
Adequate medical facilities	129	37.2	127	36.6	57	16.4	34	9.8	3.0115	Accepted
Reconstruction	87	25.1	145	41.8	65	18.7	50	14.4	2.7752	Accepted
Sufficient monetary donation and adequate family welfare to emergency victims	105	30.3	158	45.5	34	9.8	50	14.4	2.9164	Accepted
Counselling support needs to address traumatic experience	73	21.0	176	50.7	65	18.7	33	9.5	2.8329	Accepted
Relationship building support needs to address social isolation	81	23.3	177	51.0	53	15.3	36	10.4	2.8732	Accepted
Livelihood activities support needs to address economic challenges	98	28.2	167	48.1	40	11.5	42	12.1	2.9251	Accepted
Spiritual needs to address social life changes	89	25.6	120	34.6	80	23.1	58	16.7	2.6916	Accepted

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Table 1 above described the statements on the immediate needs of the emergency victims in Kano State. According to the Table, responses on the statement on the security of the life and property of the respondents were strongly agreed by 188 (54.2%) of the sampled. This was followed by 81 (23.3%) who agreed with the said statement on security of life and property. While 42 (12.1%) strongly disagreed, only 36 (10.4%) disagreed with the statement as their immediate need. The mean 3.19 indicated the acceptance of the statement that security of life and property is an immediate need of emergency victims. When the statement on comfortable shelter as an immediate need was stated, 158 (45.5%) strongly agreed with it. This was followed by 116 (33.4%) who opined that comfortable shelter was an immediate need of emergency victims. While a small percentage 9.2 (32) disagreed with the said statement, only 41 (11.8%) strongly disagreed with the statement that comfortable shelter was an immediate need of emergency victims. The mean score 3.12 indicated the acceptance that comfortable shelter was an immediate need of emergency victims. However, those who strongly agreed that essential foodstuff was an immediate need of emergency victims constituted 172 (49.6%). This

was followed by a reasonable percentage 30.5 (106) who agreed with the said statement. Added to this were 39 (11.2%) who disagreed with the said statement. This was complemented with the remaining 30 (8.6%) who strongly disagreed with the statement on essential food stuff was an immediate need of emergency victims. The mean score 3.21 indicated the acceptance of the statement that essential food stuff was an immediate need of emergency victims. Regarding the statement that adequate medical facilities was an immediate need of emergency victims, those who strongly agreed and those agreed with the statement were 129 (37.2%) and 127 (36.6%). These were followed by those who disagreed with the said statement 57 (16.4%). The remaining 34 (9.8%) strongly disagreed with that adequate medical facilities were an immediate need of emergency victims. The mean score 3.01 indicated the acceptance of the statement that adequate medical facilities were an immediate need of emergency victims. Furthermore, (148) 41.8% agreed with the statement that reconstruction was an immediate need of emergency victims. This was followed by 87 (25.1%) who strongly agreed with said statement. While (65) 18.7% disagreed, a reasonable percentage 14.4 (50) strongly disagreed as well. The mean score 2.77 indicated the acceptance of the statement that reconstruction was an immediate need of emergency victims. Looking in to the table, it is observed that highest percentage 45.5 (158) agreed with the statement that sufficient monetary donation and adequate family welfare were immediate needs of the emergency victims. This was followed by 105 (30.3%) who strongly agreed. While 50 (14.4%) strongly disagreed, only 34 (9.8%) disagreed with the statement that sufficient monetary donation and adequate family welfare was an immediate need of the emergency victims. The mean score 2.91 indicated the acceptance of the statement that sufficient monetary donation and adequate family welfare was an immediate need of emergency victims. It has been observed that (176) 50.7% agreed with the statement that counselling support needs to address traumatic experience were an immediate need of emergency victims. This was complemented by (73) 21% who strongly agreed with the said statement. While a sound percentage 18.7 (65) disagreed with the statement, only (33) 9.5% strongly disagreed. The mean score 2.83 indicated the acceptance of the statement that counselling support needs to address traumatic experience was an immediate need of emergency victims. In addition to this were (177) 51% who agreed with the statement that relationship building support needs to address social isolation were the immediate needs of emergency victims. This was followed by (81) 23.3% who strongly agreed with the said statement. While a negligible percentage 10.4 (36) strongly disagreed with the said statement, a sound 53 (15.3%) disagreed with the statement that relationship building support needs to address social isolation were the immediate needs of emergency victims. The mean score 2.87 indicated the acceptance of the statement that relationship building support needs to address social isolation were immediate need of emergency victims. Moreover, (167) 48.1% agreed with the statement that livelihood activities support needs to address economic challenges were the immediate needs of emergency victims. Only (98) 28.2% strongly agreed with the said statement and those who disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement were (40) 11.5% and (42) 12.1%. the mean score 2.92 indicated the acceptance of the statement that livelihood activities support needs to address economic challenges were immediate need of emergency victims. While 89 (25.6%) strongly agreed with the statement that spiritual needs to address social life challenges were the immediate needs of emergency victims, the highest percentage 34.6 (120) agreed with the statement, unlike (80) 23.1% who disagreed with the statement and another 58 (16.7%) who also strongly disagreed with it. The mean score 2.69 indicated the acceptance of the statement that spiritual needs to address social life changes was an immediate need of emergency victims.

These statements on the immediate needs of emergency victims were considered accepted by the respondents as justified by the cumulative mean score of 2.95 that is higher than the decision rule of 2.50 in favour of the acceptance of the statements provided in the items of the

questionnaire. From the above analysed data, it was concluded that the immediate needs of the emergency victims at various levels are diverse and become the primary role of the SEMA to effectively and efficiently deliver their services to improve the lives and living conditions of the emergency victims.

Research Question2: What is the level of satisfaction on relief services provided to emergency victims in Kano State?

Table 2. Level of Satisfaction on Relief Services Provided to Emergency Victims in Kano State

Level of Satisfaction on Relief Services	High		Medium		Low		Decision
	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Provision of counselling services	82	23.6	179	51.6	86	24.8	Medium
Provision of housing	94	27.1	163	47.0	90	25.9	Medium
Provision of food items	101	29.1	164	47.3	82	23.6	Medium
Provision of home utensils	68	19.6	122	35.2	157	45.3	Low
Provision of clothing materials	70	20.2	183	52.7	93	27.1	Medium
Provision of building materials	147	42.4	122	35.2	78	22.5	High
Provision of medical facilities	84	24.2	165	47.6	98	28.3	Medium
Provision of agricultural facilities	161	46.4	88	25.4	98	28.2	High
Provision of capacity building materials	172	49.6	84	24.2	91	26.3	High
Provision of monetary donation	126	36.3	84	24.2	137	39.5	Low

Table 2 is on the level of satisfaction on relief services provided to emergency victims who benefitted from the relief services provided by SEMA in Kano. From this Table, it was observed that (179) 51.6% of the respondents agreed with the statement that the level of the provision of counselling services was medium among the emergency victims. This was followed by (86) 24.8% of the respondents who agreed with statement that the level of the provision of counselling services was low among the emergency victims. The remaining 82 (23.6.%) of the respondents were those who believed with the statement that the level of the provision of counselling services was high among the emergency victims. However, the highest (163) 47% of the respondents agreed with the statement that the level of the provision of housing was medium among the emergency victims. This was followed by (94) 27.1% of the respondents who agreed with the statement that the level of the provision of housing was high among the emergency victims. The remaining (90) (25.9%) of the respondents believed with the statement that the level of the provision of housing was low among the emergency victims. In addition to this were (164) 47.3% of the respondents who agreed with the statement that the level of the provision of food items was medium among the emergency victims. While (101) 29.1% of the respondents agreed that the level of the provision of food items was high, sound percentage of 23.6 (82) of the respondents believed that the level of the provision of food items

among the emergency victims was low. As such, these were contrary to the (157) 45.3% of the respondents who agreed with the statement that the level of the provision of home utensils among the emergency victims was low; (68) 19.6% of the respondents agreed with the statement that the level of the provision of home utensils was high among the emergency victims. The remaining 35.2% (122) of the respondents agreed with the statement that the level of the provision of home utensils was medium. Furthermore, 183 (52.7%) of the respondents agreed that the level of the provision of clothing materials among the emergency victims was medium. This was followed by 93 (27.1%) of the respondents who believed that the level of the provision of clothing materials among the emergency victims was low. The remaining 70 (20.2%) of the respondents agreed that the level of the provision of clothing materials among the emergency victims was high.

From this table also, respondents who agreed with the statement that the level of the provision of building materials was high among the emergency victims constituted 147 (42.4%). These were followed by 122 (35.2%) of the respondents who agreed with the statement that the level of the provision of building materials was medium among the emergency victims. The remaining 78 (22.5%) of the respondents believed that the level of the provision of building materials was low among the emergency victims. Added to these were (165) 47.6% who agreed with the statement that the level of the provision of medical facilities was medium among the emergency victims. This was followed by (84) 24.2% of the respondents who agreed with the statement that the level of the provision of medical facilities was high among the emergency victims. The remaining 98 (28.3%) of the respondents agreed with the statement that the level of the provision of medical facilities was low among the emergency victims. However, the highest percentage (46.4) 161 of the respondents agreed with the statement that the level of the provision of agricultural facilities was high among the emergency victims. This were followed by 98 (28.2%) of the respondents who believed that the level of the provision of agricultural facilities was low among the emergency victims. The remaining 88 (25.4%) of the respondents opined that the level of the provision of agricultural facilities was medium among the emergency victims.

Moreover, the highest percentage (49.6) 172 agreed with the statement that the level of the provision of capacity building materials was high among the emergency victims. This was followed by (91) 26.3% of the respondents who agreed with the statement that the level of the provision of capacity building materials was low. The remaining 84 (24.2%) of the respondents agreed with the statement that the level of the provision of capacity building materials was medium among the emergency victims. Also, (126) 36.3% agreed with the statement that the level of monetary donation was high among the emergency victims. While (84) 24.2% of the respondents agreed with the statement that the level of the provision of monetary donation was medium among the emergency victims, the highest percentage 39.5 (137) of the respondents believed that the level of the provision of monetary donation was low among the emergency victims. Conclusively, the majority of the respondents at each of the statements from the above analysed data opined that the level of satisfaction of the emergency victims on relief services provided by the SEMA was medium.

Hypothesis Testing Hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between the needs of victim of emergencies and satisfaction on the relief services provided by KSEMA

Below is the table for Ho1:

Table 2: Needs and Satisfaction on Relief Services among Emergency Victims in Kano State

Variable	N	r	df	P	Remark
Needs	347	.694	345	0.01	SR
Satisfaction	347				

Table 2 indicates a positive relationship between needs and satisfaction on relief services among emergency victims in Kano State. The statistical computation indicated $r = .694$ df 345, ($P < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected on the account that significant relationship exists.

Findings

From the proceeding data analysis, the following findings were deduced:

- i. The immediate needs of the emergency victims are the security of lives and properties, comfortable shelter, essential food stuff, adequate medical facilities, reconstructions, sufficient monetary donations, adequate family welfare, counselling support, relationship building, livelihood activities and spiritual needs to address social, economic and psychological challenges.
- ii. The level of satisfaction on relief services provided to emergency victims in Kano State was medium.
- iii. There is significant relationship between the needs and satisfaction on relief services among emergency victims in Kano State.

Discussion of Findings

The first finding of this study revealed that the immediate needs of the emergency victims are the security of lives and properties, comfortable shelter, essential food stuff, adequate medical facilities, reconstructions, sufficient monetary donations, adequate family welfare, counselling support, relationship building, livelihood activities and spiritual needs to address social, economic and psychological challenges. This finding relates to the findings of the study conducted by Aminu (2018); which identified security, housing, accommodation, feeding, medication, clothing, education, empowerment, job and repatriation as the immediate needs of the emergency victims in Kumbotso local government area of Kano State. Unlike to this study's finding, and in a study undertaken by Silove, Steel and Psychol (2006), entitled understanding community psychosocial needs after disaster: implications for mental health services, authors maintained that the psycho-social needs of victims of disasters need to be addressed; priorities should be pursued in relation to mental health interventions, with most controversy surrounding the relevance of traumatic stress to mental health among the emergency victims. The views by the researchers suggested that acute traumatic stress may be a normative response to life threat, which tends to subside once conditions of safety are established. At the same time, there was a residual minority of emergency victims who might continue to experience chronic posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and their needs can be easily overlooked. Therefore, it is of great importance to address the needs of emergency victims based on their opinions regarding what may have implications to their well-being during resettlement in to their various families, communities and occupations.

The second findings of this study which revealed that the level of satisfaction on relief services provided to emergency victims in Kano State was medium. This finding relates with the study entitled Emergency Preparedness and Response to Ibadan Flood Disaster 2011: Implications for Well-being by Adejuwon and Aina (2014), both qualitative and quantitative methods were used in collecting data for the study. Findings of the study revealed that the flood disaster was

caused by acts of man and nature. Also, the affected community in Ibadan was not effectively informed to enable them to prepare for the flood disaster by the state emergency agencies due to financial constraints and an ineffective communication system. Although the various emergency agencies within the state and the country fairly responded when the flood occurred, the disaster could not be managed due to lack of adequately trained personnel for response and rescue operations and inadequate equipment. The study made recommendations to the public and appropriate authorities so as to improve the well-being of victims, such as the provision of an institutional approach to disaster management by the state government's SEMA and LEMA at local government levels.

The finding of the hypothesis revealed that there is significant relationship between the needs and satisfaction on relief services among emergency victims in Kano State. The null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that a significant relationship exists between the between the needs and satisfaction on relief services among emergency victims in Kano State. The finding is in line with the findings by Enwemeka (2014) which revealed the administration of emergency relief programmes in Nigeria particularly in Delta State has suffered a setback following the ineffectiveness of the public/government agencies discharged with disaster management and the pattern of administration of emergency relief programmes in Delta State places.

Conclusion

It was observed that the level of the satisfaction on the relief services rendered to emergency victims was provided at medium to its beneficiaries in Kano State, despite lots of inadequacies in terms of community participation, low facilities, poor external support, lack of emergency management agency at local governments level and many others. Hence, humanitarian support services can also arise from educational perspectives. Also, humanitarian development during crises or disasters comprised of educational support services in form of literacy, vocational, and occupational training that will facilitate community care services in form of voluntary participation of individual philanthropists, NGOs, external donations and many more.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i) KSEMA should set a mobilization committee that will involve staff and stakeholders that will educate members of the public in disaster preparedness and management so as to effectively manage the occurrence of disasters in the State.
- ii) Government and non-governmental organisations should mobilise other sources of external assistance/donations for supporting the provision of sufficient monetary donations that will facilitate occupational choices and career development among the emergency victims.

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